

Assessment of Environmental Air Pollution from Charcoal Production In Apa Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the assessment of environmental air pollution from charcoal production in Apa local government area of Benue State, Nigeria. Questionnaire and Semi-Structured interview were used for data collection. MultiRAE lite QRAE systems multigas sampler was used to monitor the concentration of Nitrous oxide (NO and NO₂), Carbon monoxide (CO), Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Sulphur dioxide (SO₂); Dust track II Aerosol monitor R11593 for measuring suspended particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}). Data collected were analyzed using inferential (Correlation analysis) and descriptive statistic (mean and standard deviation). The mean±SD (ppm) concentrations of pollutants monitored across the wards were CO: 16.4±0.35; CO₂: 41.28±1.73; NO₂: 0.63±0.5; SO₂: 2.17±0.09; PM₁₀: 131.92±1.99 and PM_{2.5}: 42.83±1.95. PM₁₀ had the highest mean concentration. The recommends environmental awareness and education should be embarked upon in the rural areas to sensitize the residents to the health problems associated with exposure to high level air pollutants and ensure compliance with local regulations and standards for air pollution emissions.

Keywords: Assessment , Environment, Health and Charcoal Production

Introduction

Charcoal is the primary energy source for cooking, as well as major source of income generation and environmental degradation in rural areas of most African countries including Nigeria (Kammen and Lew, 2005). Charcoal production is a vital ecological service provided by dry forest and woodlands. Increased population and continuous outrageous increases in the pricing of alternative energy sources, particular kerosene, have given significance to the charcoal business, which is currently spreading rapidly across Nigeria.

Although fuel-wood is an important source of energy for domestic use in rural areas but is also a major source of air pollutants such as carbon monoxide, particulate matters, Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and others which are detrimental to human health. Poverty, lack

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and/or inadequacy of alternative energy sources have promoted the use of fuel-wood which creates high levels of air pollutants (Zafar et al., 2010). Exposure to these substances leads to increased risk of a variety of diseases including pneumonia, chronic respiratory diseases and lung cancer (Bruce et al., 2002).

Biomass fuel smoke has been classified as a probable human carcinogen and coal smoke as a proven human carcinogen, mutagens (WHO, 1997) and is as dangerous to health as breathing in emissions from a car exhaust or tobacco smoke (Koning et al., 1985). Comparison of the burden of illness and premature death from solid fuel use (e.g. fuel-wood) with other major risk factors, including outdoor air pollution, tobacco smoking and hypertension indicated that solid fuel use may be responsible for 800,000 to 2.4 million premature deaths each year (Ezzati et al., 2002; Smith et al., 2004). Inhaled air pollutants have diverse effects on people that are exposed, depending on body constitution, lifestyle, nutritional status and age. Studies have shown that women and children, who are the most exposed and vulnerable to the pollutants, are two to six times at risk of contracting serious respiratory infections (Jones, 1999). Interest in respiratory health impacts of air pollutants from fuel-wood utilization has been increasing rapidly probably as a result of high cases of illnesses recorded. Traynor et al., (1985) among rural women and children observed that long time exposure to biomass combustion results in chronic obstructive lung diseases, heart diseases, acute respiratory infections, low birth weight, eye disorder, conjunctivitis, blindness and cancer (Edokpa and Ikelegbe, 2012). Children strapped on their mothers' back while cooking with open cook stoves contracted pneumococcal infections 2.5 times higher than non-exposed ones (WHO, 1997; Mac, 2009).

United Nations Development Program (UNDP 2005) affirmed that aside from the effects of charcoal production on the environment, there are also human health-related challenges. These include backache, heat, and cough, among other ailments, which are experienced a lot by charcoal producers. Repetitively moving heavy woods during charcoal production induces lumbar pain and muscular soreness to the producers (Tzanakis et al., 2011). It is worth noting that some charcoal producers lose their lives during the production. Accidents may also occur during the cutting of trees, kiln preparation, and loading of charcoal onto Lorries. Furthermore, producers inhale gases and smoke, and the heat produced during the charcoal production is a source of ailments, such as respiratory diseases and cough. They also experience sore hands, fatigue, and chest pain. Sputum production, dyspnea, and hemoptysis are other ailments suffered by the producers. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2017: World Bank, 2011) confirmed that in very inefficient operations, charcoal production can result into 9kg of CO₂ per kilogram of charcoal produced and 29-62%, 28-61% and 9-18% of emissions are from wood sourcing, carbonization of wood into charcoal and end use.

Statement of Problem

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Inefficient production and utilization of charcoal has linked to several environmental and health problem. Globally, over 4 million deaths occur annually from illnesses related to the smoke generated by indoor combustion, which mainly affects women and small children (World Health Organisation [WHO] 2006). The negative effects of charcoal production on the environment and health have raised a growing concern among policy makers concern with the management of forest resources. Charcoal production poses significant environmental and health risks, including deforestation, air pollution, and negative impacts on human health, particularly in communities surrounding the production areas. The unsustainable harvesting of wood for charcoal production contributes to forest degradation, loss of biodiversity, and increased greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, the combustion of charcoal and exposure to pollutants can lead to respiratory problems, cardiovascular disease, and other health issues. This problem affects not only the environment but also the well-being and livelihoods of communities dependent on natural resources (Tzanakis et al., 2018).

Charcoal production poses significant environmental and health risks, including deforestation, air and water pollution, and negative impacts on human health, particularly in communities surrounding production areas. The unsustainable harvesting of wood for charcoal production contributes to forest degradation, loss of biodiversity, and increased greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, the combustion of charcoal and exposure to pollutants can lead to respiratory problems, cardiovascular disease, and other health issues. This problem affects not only the environment but also the well-being and livelihoods of communities dependent on natural resources (Bailis, et al., 2005).

Hence, the need to understand the environmental implications of charcoal production in Apa LGA with a view to adopting production strategies that will ameliorate the physical impacts of charcoal production in Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

- i. Examine the environmental impact of charcoal production on air quality in the study area

Research Questions

- i. What is the environmental impact of charcoal production on air quality in the study area?

Materials and Method

Apa LGA is located between Latitudes 7°.6296 N and 7° 8711E. It is bounded in the north by Agatu LGA, to the East by Gwer West, to the south by Otukpo and West by Omala LGA of Kogi State while Agatu Local Government Area is located between Latitudes 7° 9061N and Longitude 7° 8549E. It is bounded in the north by Nassarawa and Apa LGA to the south and Kogi to the East and Gwer West to the West. Geographically, Benue State lies within the Middle Belt region of Nigeria and is characterized by diverse landscapes. The southern part of the state features lowland areas and river valleys, including the Benue River, which is a significant waterway in

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the region. Towards the north, the terrain gradually transitions into the Guinea Savanna, characterized by grassland plains and scattered woodland. The local Government has eleven (11) wards (Auke, Edikwu I, Edikwu II, Igoro, Ikobi, Iga Okpaya, Oba wards, Ugbokpo, Oiji, Ofuoke, and Ojantelle/Akpete). The Local government Area has a population of about 96,780 people and a land area of about 995km² (National population commission of Nigeria, 2006).

The air quality assessment was conducted in the dry season when the charcoal production activities are pronounced. Wind vane was used to determine the wind direction; the MultiRAE lite QRAE systems multigas sampler was used to monitor the concentration of Nitrous oxide (NO and NO₂), Carbon monoxide (CO), Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Sulphur dioxide (SO₂); Dust track II Aerosol monitor R11593 for measuring suspended particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}). These gases are emitted during wood combustion and are known to induce or cause respiratory disease in exposed humans and also contribute to the problem of global warming (NO₂ and CO₂ being greenhouse gases). These gases were monitored in replicates, in each of the communities between November, 2012 and January, 2013. The results were compared with the WHO (world health organization) permissible limits for 24hours concentration of these gases in the ambient environments to determine the compliance level of emissions from the charcoal production sites. Data collected was analyzed using inferential (Correlation analysis) and descriptive statistic (mean and standard deviation) using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

Results

Table 1: Location of Charcoal Production Sites in Apa LGA

Ward	Latitude	Longitude
Iga okpaya	7.530918	7.873710
Ugbokpo	7.648945	7.874932
Oshigbudu	7.828283	7.858491
Ojantele	7.740790	7.895094
Oiji	7.575317	7.935829
Oba	7.562768	7.841572
Auke	7.504300	7.771974
Ikobi	7.747389	8.008851
Edikwu ward I	7.664519	7.983623
Edikwu ward II	7.601851	7.970475
Igoro	7.690009	7.838660

The geographical positioning of the sampling points are presented in Table 1. In order to assess the environmental and health impact of charcoal production in Apa Local Government Area of Benue State, air quality assessment were carried out. The air measurements samples were collected across the different wards from the local government areas (Iga okpaya, Ugbokpo, Oshigbudu, Ojantele, Oiji, Oba, Auke, Ikobi, Edikwu ward I, Edikwu ward II and Igoro).

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Figure 1: Benue State, showing Apa LGA and Air Sampling Sites
 Source: Benue State Geographic and Information System

Table 2: Ambient Air Concentration at the production sites

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Ward	CO(PPM)	CO ₂ (PPM)	NO ₂ (PPM)	SO ₂ (PPM)	PM ₁₀ (PPM)	PM _{2.5} (PPM)
Oiji	15.7±0.12	25.21±0.32	0.62±0.0	1.45±0.01	164.1±2.19	61.50±1.68
Oba	21.8±1.13	52.99±2.36	0.63±0.2	3.67±0.00	152.6±1.95	33.81±1.04
Igaya Opkaya	18.4±0.09	34.09±2.19	0.55±0.0	1.69±0.01	115.1±1.69	46.97±2.19
Ugbokpo	19.7±0.32	38.19±1.61	0.54±0.0	1.98±0.02	125.3±1.43	38.20±1.98
Ojantele	14.10±0.11	34.98±1.61	0.63±0.1	2.78±0.29	131.2±1.31	36.00±3.10
Auke	8.7±0.31	62.19±2.26	0.78±0.0	1.46±0.21	103.2±3.41	40.50±1.74
Mean±Stdev	16.4±0.35	41.28±1.73	0.63±0.5	2.17±0.09	131.92±1.9	42.83±1.95
WHO Permissible Limit	10.0-20.0	NA	0.04-0.06	0.01-0.1	NA	NA

***NA-Not Available**

The mean concentration of CO among the wards ranged between 8.70±0.31 and 21.8±1.13 ppm which was slightly above the permissible limit with an overall mean value of 16.4±0.35 ppm, which is within the permissible limit (10 -20 ppm) allowed by WHO (WHO, 2005). Carbon dioxide (CO₂) ranged between 25.21±0.32 and 62.19±0.22 ppm with an overall mean value of 41.28±1.73 ppm. Particulate Matter i.e. PM₁₀ have mean concentration that ranged between 103.2±3.41 and 164.1±2.19 ppm, an overall mean of 131.92±1.9, PM_{2.5} ranged between 36.00±3.10 and 61.50±1.68 ppm, and an overall mean value of 42.83±1.95 ppm. NO₂ ranged between 0.54±0.00 and 0.78±0.00 ppm with an overall mean value of 0.63±0.5, which were higher than the WHO limit of 0.06 ppm (WHO, 2005), SO₂ ranged between 1.45±0.01 and 3.67±0.00 ppm with an overall mean value of 2.17±0.09. trend is not the same for NO₂, SO₂ and CH₄. The mean value of CO observed in this study was lower unlike Oguntoke et al., (2010), however the trend may not be unconnected to some phenomenon that may affect pollutants' concentration in an outdoor environment. Such factors include temperature inversion, atmospheric stability, lapse rate and mixing height.

Conclusion

Utilization of fuel-wood as a source of energy is a major source of air pollution in the study area. Apart from the fact that these gases affect human health negatively, their eventual release into the ambient environment is capable of increasing the concentration of air pollutants in the already polluted atmosphere. The mean±SD (ppm) concentrations of pollutants monitored

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across the wards were CO: 16.4±0.35; CO₂: 41.28±1.73; NO₂: 0.63±0.5; SO₂: 2.17±0.09; PM₁₀: 131.92±1.99 and PM_{2.5}: 42.83±1.95. PM₁₀ had the highest mean concentration.

Recommendations

- i. Environmental awareness and education should be embarked upon in the rural areas to sensitize the residents to the health problems associated with exposure to high level air pollutants.
- ii. Ensure compliance with local regulations and standards for air pollution emissions.

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